

EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF HISTORY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: *This article explains in detail the importance of history as an independent social science that has its place in all stages of education in educating a harmoniously developed generation.*

Key words: *model, transformation, combination, assimilation, information-communication.*

Introduction:

Before thinking about the effective organization of the science of history, it is useful to study the concept of "effective education" by analyzing the views of local and foreign researchers. Effective teaching is an educational process in which teachers combine the different teaching methods or use them individually to develop students' ability to learn independently, to understand the lesson atmosphere, and to acquire the necessary knowledge. is a concept.

In the process of teaching history, the preparation of materials based on their interaction with other social sciences, such as geography, civics, religious culture, and ethics, not only helps students better understand topics, but also allows them to understand social realities and real life in general.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Effective teaching is a complex set of different processes designed to improve the quality of education. There are two main characteristics of effective teaching. These are:

- Facilitate students' learning of a variety of facts, skills, values, and concepts;
- Develop in teachers the ability to use different teaching strategies, methods and technologies, either individually or in combination, rather than a single course in the classroom;

According to another view, effective education can be described as a key teaching skill needed to increase student achievement. In the context of these ideas, it can be said that an effective teacher knows and loves his profession and field, is knowledgeable, diligent, selfless, disciplined and enterprising, has the ability to make quick and correct decisions, is fair and

at the same time able to promote knowledge to students and their peace and is defined as a person who is interested in the future.

Quality of education is a qualitative process of the components of the entire education system, a process with complex dynamics, which is explained by changes in the activities of educational institutions, ie changes in their social, economic, technological and political environment. At the same time, the quality of modern education is not one of the results of innovative development, but one of the prerequisites for its implementation.

Effective history teaching requires students to provide sources and evidence, along with ready-made historical conclusions. From a pedagogical point of view, it is very effective for a student to develop historical knowledge and imagination by analyzing certain historical sources (whether written or oral). Indeed, in history lessons, it is more useful to use methods that encourage the learner's independent thinking than methods that stimulate the learner's memory.

Results:

"History", a Western alternative to the concept of history, belongs to the ancient Greek language and means "research" or the study of truth. As a science, history studies human history through its unique methodology. Historical methodology, identifying a research area, problem or topic, developing hypotheses related to that topic or problem, gathering information from evidence and sources, analyzing and criticizing this information, reviewing and understanding other research on the topic, as well as logically interpreted research consists of giving. Based on this, the role of the historian is defined as the study of the past in the process of his independent scientific development, the creation of clear, realistic and complete concepts or descriptions of the subject, and thinking about all these stages.

The role of the history teacher is to teach historical concepts as well as to transmit them into the future. To be effective in teaching history, a history teacher must have a certain level of knowledge and some teaching skills, and the ability to transform, interpret, evaluate, analyze, and synthesize historical events, facts, people, processes, and identities.

Discussion:

The use of fiction in history lessons also helps to clarify historical truth and create vivid images of the past. In addition, the use of a variety of demonstrations is effective in narrating historical events. For example, visual representations of objects of material culture, technical (audio-visual) means of teaching. All of this allows students to imagine the environment of a historical period, to feel themselves in the midst of historical events in the past.

The current state of education requires a rethinking and clarification of the concept of education, and a process of analyzing the categories and principles of person-centered pedagogy. The new model of pedagogical consciousness will gradually abandon the practice of direct teacher influence on the learner and will allow the learner to more effectively organize the structure of the entire pedagogical space to enable him or her to develop. In this way, each teacher strives to make their lessons interesting and meaningful, which increases the learners' interest in the topic.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the use of historical materials and resources in the history lesson is very important and useful. In addition, the use of information and communication technologies and the Internet in history lessons not only contributes to the intellectual development of students, but also increases their level of historical thinking and learning.

In particular, history lessons focus on the development of the individual through the development of the values of different eras, the ability to put oneself in the place of the past, to understand his thoughts and actions, rather than to assimilate facts. All of this can be done using historical empathy.

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